

Online Forum Re:dy Service

Qualitative Study

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DCMK

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Executive Summary

Re:dy service evaluation and re:dy users typologies

1. Re:dy Service is perceived as a service that allows to monitor and manage energy consumption at a rational level. At an emotional level, a service that satisfies the need for Relaxation/ Worries Free and Comfort because everything is under control. A reliable and convenient service that allows users to access their real energy consumption, avoiding unexpected surprises regarding energy costs and to monitor, control and optimize the household energy consumption.
2. Based on users level of knowledge of the service, equipment owned and used and the number and type of re:dy service functionalities used, five typologies of users were identified. The majority of interviewees were Heavy Users. These interviewees tend to be younger (on their 40's) and more tech savvy than Basic Users (on their 50's).
 - a) **Heavy Users** tend to be tech-savvy, have a medium or even a high knowledge of the Re:dy Service, tend to be involved with the service, searching for information, exploring the full potential of the service. For them the re:dy service is a way to control and manage their energy consumption in order to optimize and reduce costs. They tend to access the service frequently through a Smartphone since they value to access real time information at anytime and anywhere. They tend to have five to six plugs and a re:dy meter since their main focus is to control as many appliances as possible. Heavy Users tend to use control and energy efficiency functionalities to optimize their household energy consumption. They are globally satisfied with Re:dy Service as the service meets their expectations, delivering what it promises, generates cost reduction and it's easy to set up and manage.
 - b) **Basic Users** tend to have a low knowledge of the Re:dy Service, however, they seem eager to learn more about the service and learn from other users experiences. Their main goal is to implement behaviors for greater energy efficiency. Re:dy service is a way for Basic Users to gather information that allows them to implement energy saving measures, manually. They tend to access the service once a month through their laptop since it is a way to access more detailed information. They tend to use a reduced number of functionalities, mainly control functionalities and simulators. Overall, Basic Users tend to be satisfied with Re:dy Service since it allows them to lower energy costs. Nevertheless, some interviewees consider that they are not able to use the service's full potential mainly due to their lack of knowledge regarding Re:dy functionalities.

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Re:dy service evaluation and re:dy users typologies

- c) **Producers Basic Users** tend to have some similarities to the Basic Users typology however they are more focused on controlling energy production as well as energy consumption. They tend to access the service weekly or biweekly mainly through their computer. They tend to have a plug or none since they tend to have low knowledge about the service.
- d) **Producers Heavy Users** tends to have some similarities to the Heavy Users typology however these interviewees are also focused on controlling energy production as well as optimize energy consumption. This typology of users are the one that tend access the service more frequently, namely several times a day. Producers Heavy Users are globally satisfied with Re:dy Service, however their expectation is to receive more information about the energy consumption per household division/ room.
- e) **Observers Users** tend to have a low knowledge about the Re:dy Service and tend to use the service only to monitor energy consumption. The interaction with the service is almost limited to the monthly analysis of the re:dy report.
- f) Although the equipment prices tend to be a barrier, the plugs tend to be highly valued and desired as perceptively only with this equipment interviewees can benefit of the service full potential. The Re:dy Meter tends to be only known by heavy users, perceptively this equipment has the same function as the plugs but for built in electric equipment/ household appliances.

Executive Summary

Evaluation of access devices to re:dy service

3. Smartphones are mainly used by interviewees that tend to access the re:dy service frequently and value the possibility of accessing anytime from anywhere, mainly Heavy Users and Producers Heavy Users. However, the main challenge of this device is that not all functionalities and tools seem to be present in the re:dy service App thus limiting the interaction with the service. On the other, the laptop tends to be used mainly by Basic Users and Producers Basic Users Typologies since all the functionalities and information are accessible in this device. The tablet as very accessible and easy to use and tends to be used by Heavy Users and Producers Heavy Users since it is a good alternative to a smartphone.

Portal Assessment

4. The re:dy service Portal tends to be very well evaluated since it is perceived as a user friendly and intuitive portal with well structured and detailed information. The Home Screen is perceived as very good starting point as it displays the most relevant information in a direct, appealing and easy to interpret way. The Active Management Menu and My Consumption – Energy menu is mainly used by Heavy Consumers as these interviewees have a higher knowledge of the service and equipment that allows them to take advantage of these functionalities. Globally, for interviewees a Help Section would be valued not only to overcome some difficulties and to fully seize the service potential.

Executive Summary

Re:dy service functionalities exploration

5. The Forecast functionality is valued due to the possibility of detecting deviations to the normal energy consumption and adopting corrective measures as well as knowing the ahead the value of the electric energy monthly cost. Profiles are perceived as relevant for the majority of interviewees as perceptively they allow users to easily adjust the functioning of the equipment to specific needs. However, these interviewees tend not to know how to use it or don't have the equipment to do it. Thus it's only used by a minority of Heavy Users. The presence simulator although useful is perceived as somewhat difficult to program. The functionality comparison of families/households tends to be perceived as a less useful functionality at the moment as it does not seem to be fully operational. Power and Tariff Simulator, Schedule re:dy meter plugs operating hours and Take control on the limit of contracted power are Energy efficiency functionalities and tend to be used mainly by Heavy Users and Producers Heavy Users. Basic Users generally aren't aware of these functionalities or know them but don't know how to use them. Although not all users are aware of the different types of alerts/notices that the re:dy service provides, these functionalities are perceived as useful functionalities to draw user's attention to a potential problem and in this sense tend to be valued.
6. Regarding new functionalities, Heavy Users tend to suggest functionalities that increase comfort in the household and control over the household electric equipment such as Household Temperature Control and Household Alarm. When confronted with the possibility of re:dy service to learn with users operations (and be more proactive) interviewees tend to value this possibility since this idea is consistent with functionality's already present in the re:dy service. Also, this conveys the idea that the service continues to evolve which can generate more interest and involvement and helps to justify the service monthly fee. The interviewees welcomed the possibility of sharing experiences with other users and, in this context, suggested the idea of having an Online Forum. Perceptively this will help to clarify doubts, to learn with other users experience and to improve how users interact with the re:dy service.

Executive Summary

Re:dy service challenges and recommendations

7. The lack of knowledge, although in different levels, tends to be a challenge for all users. In this sense to overcome this challenge it's important to create Video Tutorials, a Live Chat Assistance in the re:dy service portal and mainly for Basic Users and Producers Basic Users, an Online Forum where clients can share experiences and clarify doubts.
8. The lack of plugs is also a challenge for all users. To overcome this challenge mainly among Heavy Users and Producers Heavy Users a re:dy service campaign "Bring a friend to join re:dy service an win a plug..." might be a win-win partnership as Heavy Users can be easily re:dy service advocators, promoting this service among potential clients while winning more equipment that allows them to further interact with the service. On the other hand, the possibility of acquiring plugs and re:dy meter with the cost divided in monthly payments could also be a good idea to increase re:dy service involvement and interaction.

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7. Main Objectives and Methodology

A service that allows monitor and manage energy consumption at an rational level. At an emotional level, a service that satisfies the need for Relaxation/ Worries Free and Comfort because everything in under control.

Re:dy Service is mainly perceived as a **service to monitor and manage energy consumption** and, in this context, it's associated with values such as :

- **Efficiency;**
- **Optimization;**
- **Profitability;**
- **Economy,**
- **Saving;**
- **Automation**

"It allows me to control how much I have to expend and collect at the end of every billing period. Nowadays I use the Re:dy service to monitor how much I will have to give EDP and also how much will I receive from EDP." (Producers Heavy Users typology, Male, 35 years old)

Furthermore, **emotionally**, the re:dy service means:

- **Control** (control my household, my expenses, my life),
... but also
- (for some interviewees) **Relax, no worries, more time for myself** (all under control),
....and
- (for some interviewees) **Comfort.**

"Relaxation, no worries, with a lot more time to myself." (Heavy Users typology, Male, 59 years old)

A service that avoids unexpected surprises regarding energy monthly costs and allows monitor, control and optimize the household energy consumption.

This service tends to be considered as a **reliable, secure, convenient** and **accessible service** that globally allows users to:

- **Know their real energy consumption** (not estimate) **and the monthly cost**– no surprises in their invoice and/or the monthly value from energy production;
- **Monitor their household energy consumption and/or production anywhere, at anytime from multiple devices;**
- **Control and analyse their household energy consumption and/or by:**
 - Using the service' analysis tools (ex. Forecast);
 - **Implement consumption notices** (ex: define a monthly budget and be warned when this budget is about to be exceeded);
- (With plugs) **Control and analyse energy consumption per equipment/plug;**
- **Optimize energy consumption by:**
 - (With plugs and/or meter) **Identify electric equipment that present an higher/excessive energy consumption and replacing them per more energy efficient ones or controlling their usage** (ex. Using them less only when really necessary or using them only in a more economic schedule);
 - **Program equipment's to work at a more economic time** (off peak hours);
 - **Eliminating energy consumption in standby;**
 - **Turning on/off electric equipment's remotely.**

"For me, the Re:dy Service is an assured way of checking my consumptions and not having any surprises on the end of the months' bill." (Heavy User typology Male, 40)

"It allows me to see online and on real time my consumptions and production level. It allows me to see a chart with Power usage (this feature allowed me to lower the contracted power and in that way, I was able to save a few euros.) It allows me to know (based on forecasts) my monthly expenses costs. It also allowed me to know, on any given moment, my energy expenses and production revenues, on a given period. The notifications are very useful. Allows me to control plugs remotely." (Producers Heavy Users, Male, 35 years old)

However the majority of interviewees consider the monthly fee too high.

Five typologies of users were identified depending on the level of knowledge of the service, the equipment owned and the number and type of functionalities used.

However user' experience, involvement and satisfaction with the Re:dy service tends to vary depending on:

- **Level of knowledge of the service, for instance:**
 - Existing functionalities and how to implement them (ex. notices, to program plugs etc.);
 - Existing analysing tools and how to use them.
- **Equipment owned and used: number of plugs and re:dy meter;**
- **Number and type of functionalities used.**

In this context their were identified 5 typologies of users of the re:dy service:

1. **Observers;**
2. **Basic Users;**
3. **Heavy Users;**
4. **Producers Basic Users;**
5. **Producers Heavy Users.**

"To set up appliances and monitor consumptions. My main goal is to reduce costs without compromising the comfort, and that can be obtain through some intelligent settings." Heavy Users - Male, 35

"With only a Click I can control what's going on with my energy consumptions." Basic User – Male , 57

"And so, the Re:dy feature I enjoy the most is the consumptions real-time information and Forecast energy estimates. I think there might be one or another feature I still haven't explored..." Producers Basic Users – Male, 63

Among the different users typologies, Heavy and Producers Heavy Users Typologies are those who have a higher knowledge and involvement with Re:dy Service.

Globally these typologies have the following main differences:

Usage Objective Access Frequency	Analyze information provided by Re:dy Service	Analyze information displayed by Re:dy Service to control energy consumption and production	Manage energy consumption with Re:dy Service	Equipment owned and used
Rarely	Observer			None
Once a month to once a week	Producers Basic Users			2 plugs and a re:dy meter
	Basic Users			
Once a week to once a day	Heavy Users & Producers Heavy Users			5 to 6 plugs and a re:dy meter
More than once a day				
Re:dy Service Level of Knowledge	Low	Medium	High	

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Heavy Users tend to be Tech-Savvy, have a medium or even a high knowledge of the Re:dy Service, are involved with the service, searching for information, exploring the full potential of the service. For them the re:dy service is a way to control and manage their energy consumption in order to optimize and reduce costs.

Who are they?

- **Interviewees aged between 35- 59 years old** (mostly on their 40's) that tend to :
 - **Be tech-savvy**, some of them have jobs related with technology (ex. computer engineer);
 - **Have a medium or high knowledge of the re:dy Service** namely know how to analyze tools and functionalities and actively use a large number of them (7 or 8).
- These interviewees tend to search for information and to explore the service to try to take advantage of the service full potential.

For what purpose do they use Re:dy Service?

- **To rationalize and optimize energy consumption on their household and reducing energy costs by:**
 1. **Monitor Energy consumption in their household** (global and per main electric equipment);
 2. **Analyze Energy consumption in their household** (global and per main electric equipment) using Re:dy Service tools;
 3. **Using Re:dy Service to implement measures to optimize and save energy** (ex. program plugs, notices etc.).
- Their main focus is to monitor as many appliances as possible, mainly the ones that have higher energy consumptions (e.g. Refrigerator, Washing machine, TV, Air Conditioner, Oven, Freezer, Heat Pump, Microwave, PC, etc.), in order to identify and implement measures to optimize energy consumption (ex. replace an home appliance with excessive energy consumption, replace regular light bulbs for energy saving bulbs).

"The features I commonly use, besides forecast, it's Profiles, to activate/deactivate the settings of already defined schedules. I also use control to activate/deactivate the plugs, and also check a specific appliance's consumption. I use a lot the feature Consumption to check on the bigger consumption schedules, Power to verify if I'm not going over the contracted energy and if necessary preform a change in rate." Heavy Users - Male, 35

" One of the features I often use, at least in the early days, is the one related to the contracted power, where I can see if the power I have contracted nowadays is the most adequate to my energy needs" Heavy Users - Male, 41

Heavy Users access to Re:dy Service once a week to twice a day, mainly through Smartphone since they value access to real time information easily and quickly at anytime at anywhere. Their focus is to control as many appliances as possible, so they tend to have 5 to 6 plugs.

How do they use Re:dy Service?

Frequency of access to re:dy service:

- **Once a week to twice a day** (majority 3 or 4 times a week) mainly from home or work to **control their energy consumption** as well as the **consumption forecast**.
- To interact with re:dy service they tend to use:
 - (Majority of interviewees) Usually: **Smartphone**;
 - (Some interviewees) Less frequently: **Tablet**;
 - (Some interviewees) Rarely, in some cases, once a month: **PC**;
- Thus, these interviewees tend to **value access to real time information easily and quickly at anytime at anywhere**.

Devices:

- **These clients tend to own 5 to 6 plugs** as their main focus is to **control as many appliances as possible**, mainly the ones that have higher energy consumption (ex. Refrigerator, Washing machine, TV, Air Conditioner, Oven, Freezer, Heat Pump, Microwave, PC, etc.), in order to identify and implement measures to optimize energy consumption (ex. replace an home appliance with excessive energy consumption for one with less energy consumption, use this equipment only at more economic hours etc.). In this context they perceive the plugs as their main source of information.
- Also, **they tend to have a re:dy meter** (4 out of 6 clients), although this equipment tends not to be as important as plugs are as a source of information and control.

"I prefer accessing the Re:dy service on my Smartphone, when I have a little time to spare I'll go in and check on consumptions, it's something that I've always have near me."
Heavy User - Male, 43

Control household energy consumption, set up plugs to control a household appliance's functioning schedule, remotely turn on/off a household appliance, energy consumption analysis/statistics and simulate best tariff and most suitable electric power are the most used functionalities by Heavy Users Typology.

What functionalities do they tend to use?

In this context, these clients tend to value and use the following functionalities:

- More frequently used:

- Control household energy consumption;
 - To take measures/adjust consumption if there's any unforeseen increase in energy consumption.
- Consumption forecasts (in € and Kw)
- Control a household appliance's energy consumption
- Set up Plugs to control a household appliance's functioning schedule;
 - Frequently used to take advantage of a more economic schedule (when energy is less expensive)
 - Tends to be valued as a tool for climate control increasing comfort in the household without increasing energy cost.
- Remotely turn on/off a household appliance /electric equipment
- Energy consumption analysis/statistics;
- Simulate best tariff and most suitable electric power;

- Less frequently used:

- Set up Operating Profiles (ex. out of home, in Holidays)
- Electric power limit control to prevent the meter to shut off;
- Set up notices:
 - Failure in plug communication;
 - Budget Control;
 - Power Failure/Cut off
- Consult energy consumption record.

"The re:dy features have gone beyond my expectations. Specially for the information provided that's so easy to interpret, and on the old days you could only get that information by telephone and it was a lot more complicated not only to interpret but also to understand. The other features I'd like to see is an Online chat service (like Whatsapp) on the Help feature. And also video demos of every type of malfunction, or a step-by-step problem solver on the website/app" " Heavy Users - Male, 40

" The Profiles [feature] is not that useful, because they are not well-implemented, they will overcome previously set Plugs settings. If I've created a Profile that told the Plugs should be turned off, they should be kept turned off despite their previous settings. " Heavy Users - Male, 35

For Heavy Users, Re:dy is a reliable, practical and useful service that provides useful and easy to understand information and analysis tools that help to better manage energy consumption, enhances the comfort of the household.

In this context, Heavy users interviewees have emphasized the following aspects as the main strengths of the re:dy service:

Main Strengths of re:dy service for Heavy Users

- **Reliable, practical and useful,**
- **Easy to install and to use to manage energy consumption in a easy and intuitive way;**
- Provides **useful and easy to understand information and analysis tools that help to better manage energy consumption** namely:
 - Energy consumption in real time of the whole household and each re:dy plugs;
 - Energy consumption of individual household appliances;
 - Energy consumption information aggregated in a specific period of time
- **Enables the automation of energy efficiency measures** namely programming the functioning of high energy consumption equipment's in off peak hours ,
- **Enhances the comfort of the household in terms of temperature by programing equipment and without increasing energy costs;**
- With **notices** that help **manage energy waste.**

Heavy Users are globally satisfied with Re:dy Service: the service meets their expectations, delivering what it promises, generates cost reduction and it's easy to set up and manage.

How do they evaluate re:dy service

- These interviewees tend to be involved and globally satisfied with re:dy Service namely since they perceive that this service:
 - Meets expectations and delivers what it promises – real-time access to energy consumption;
 - Generates cost reduction and saving;
 - It's easy to set up and manage.
- Nonetheless, some of these interviewees aren't completely satisfied with the re:dy service due to:
 - **Monthly cost perceived as too expensive**
 - The cost versus the information provided is not justified ;
 - They consider themselves as pioneers of the services and they feel they should be rewarded for this with a lower monthly subscription.
 - Perceived limited evolution of the software (computer and smartphone) that supports the service ;
 - **Some functionalities are perceived as complex and/or perceptively aren't working properly** (specially related with the re:dy plugs);
 - **The lack of information on some functionalities** leads some interviewees to identify some limitations on the service that aren't real such as: need to delete all programs when going on holidays and re-program it all when users return.
 - Not having access to all functionalities of the service on the APP
 - Some functionalities are still perceived as limited (ex. sensors should read temperature).

"The app is very limited, nowadays we practically use our smartphones to do everything, I think the app should have more access to the information such as the one we get on our PCs" Heavy Users - Male, 42

"Some features should be more flexible, for instance, Forecast only shows monthly prediction and it doesn't match my billing period." Heavy Users - Male, 59

"What I dislike is the sensors' limitation, that is, it would be ideal if I could conciliate consumption measurement with indoor house temperature measurement" Heavy Users - Male, 35

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Basic Users tend to have a low knowledge of the Re:dy Service. However, they seem eager to learn more about the service and learn from other users experiences since their main goal is to implement behaviors for greater energy efficiency.

Who are they?

- Interviewees aged between 55- 61 years old that tend to :
 - **Have a low or medium knowledge of the re:dy service.** Globally, they are aware of the main functionalities that the service provides, **although they haven't explored /don't know all the functionalities available**, frequently due to not having enough resources available to use them (ex. absence of insufficient number of plugs).
 - Nevertheless they seem eager to learn more about what the service has to offer so that they can take full advantage of it.
 - They seem open to learn from other users experiences and seem open receive advice in how to user the re:dy service – their main goal is to save energy, so they want to understand and learn the best techniques implied.
 - They tend to proactively ask for help on how to configure or program their household functionalities.

"The re:dy service ensures you of the control you have at your service. The only thing that keeps me from having a more adequate use, is the users lack of knowledge regarding the service. There should be a customer care available that can answer all doubts user may have" Basic User – Female, 55

"I was curious about the plugs pairing. As I'm applying to have 4 more, I'd like to know how to use them and take a better advantage of them!" Basic User – Female, 55

"I normally use it on the end of the month when I get EDP's notification, through my computer. I check to see how much I'm consuming. In this moment I'm not using, maximizing, checking..." Basic Users - Male, 61

"I managed to save almost 40% on my home electricity bill" Basic User – Female, 55

"As a strong point, I think that the service shows a lot of potential to be explored in the benefit of the user. AS a low point, I think that there's little information on how to explore the devices full potential." Basic Users - Male, 57

Basic Users tend to use Re:dy Service to monitor and analyze energy consumption in their household and implement energy saving measures.

For what purpose do they use Re:dy Service?

- To obtaining a more accurate information regarding their energy consumption to control it or to **optimize energy consumption on their household and reduce energy costs by:**
 1. **Monitor Energy consumption in their household** (mainly global and in some cases one or two electric equipment/household appliances);
 1. **Analyze Energy consumption in their household** (global and in some cases one or two electric equipment/household appliances) mainly using the monthly re:dy report and, in some cases some service tools;
 2. **Manually implement energy saving measures** (ex. turning on/off equipment with they aren't necessary, using equipment mainly with a higher energy consumption only in in off peak electricity hours) or using devices such as p Plug-In Timers.

*"With the Re:dy service, I can monitor my household appliances and estimate my expenses till the end of the month."
" Basic User – Female , 55*

"It helps control my expenses. I can monitor all my electric household appliances. And also, I am able to know what expenses I'm saving by the end of the month " Basic User – Female , 55

" I started to think it would be important to check my energy consumption, and I noticed that it only registers the consumption of Plugs that are turned on, logically! I confess that's why I haven't been paying much attention to the Re:dy Service. What I enjoy the less about this service is the difficulty of putting plugs on built-in appliances, or the ones that are too close to the wall, which makes it very difficult to use!" Basic User - Male, 61

" I now have the possibility to know the actual value of specific household appliances, and my consumptions evolution in general. " Basic Users - Male, 57

Basic Users access to Re:dy Service once a month to once a week through their Laptop since this platform allows them to have a more extensive access to information and therefore allows them to do more detailed analysis of their household consumptions.

How do they use Re:dy Service?

Frequency of access to re:dy service:

- **Once a month to once a week** (majority once a month mainly triggered by the reception of re:dy monthly report or the energy invoice to control/confirm their monthly consumption) generally from home.
- To interact with re:dy service the great majority of Basic Users interviewees they tend to use the **computer**.
- Perceptively this platform allows them to have a more **extensive access to information** and therefore allows them to do **more detailed analysis of their household consumptions**.

Devices:

- They tend to own **2 Plugs** although, they would like to have more but tend to refuse the extra investment necessary.
 - Some of these interviewees had problems or weren't able to pair the re:dy meter plugs or to schedule them.
- Only one of these interviewees as a re:dy meter although she doesn't know what is the purpose of this device and how to use it.

"It limits the power spent, that is, it imposes a limit to my expenses" Basic User – Male , 58

"I consider that the Re:dy service meets expectations because it allows me to have a real-time note on my consumptions. The only thing that doesn't meet my expectations is that from time to time I can't login into the App. "Basic Users - Male, 58

"About the tariffs – you must enter the option Energy Efficiency and the option optimization. There you can select one of the several options the service has. The question is, that when comparing with the actual consumption, compares with the last 30 days. As the differences on the sequential months are notorious, I propose that , it should have the possibility to compare the consumption with the homologous period. In this way, I can compare the energy consumption from February 2015 with February 2014, when my heating system is at his highest rate. "Basic Users - Male, 57

Control household energy consumption, consumption forecasts, control a household appliance's energy consumption and simulate best tariff and the most suitable electric power are the most used functionalities by Basic Users Typology.

What functionalities do they tend to use?

In this sense, these interviewees tend to use a reduced number of functionalities (2 to 4) namely:

• More frequently used:

- Control household energy consumption;
 - To analyze and try to understand for instance consumption peaks.
- Consumption forecasts (in € and Kw)
 - To know in advance the invoice amount.
- Control a household appliance's energy consumption (ex. wash and dryer, iron)
- Simulate best tariff and most suitable electric power

• Less frequently used:

- Remotely turn on/off a household appliance /electric equipment
- Set up notices.
 - It's a feature that the majority of Basic User Interviewees don't use although, some users know how to program them and when inquired they show interest in learning more about this functionality.

"I would like a better instruction manual to pair up plugs. In my opinion the Plugs size should depend on the kind of usage implied, there should be different Plug sizes so that the user could choose the best for them." Basic Users - Male, 58k

*"I agree that everything that can ease up and contribute to improve the service comprehension and the Plugs usage would be good. I confess that I haven't even access to the Profiles feature, I don't even know what it's all about."
Basic Users - Male, 61*

*"I consider that the Profiles on the feature should be defined by the user. The responsibility of what is or isn't active should rely on the user. You need the users engagement. EDP-Re:dy's main feature must be to motivate users to use the re:dy service efficiently, instead of trying to create a User profile, which I think it will always be fallible."
Basic Users - Male, 57*

Overall, Basic Users tend to be satisfied with Re:dy Service since allows them to lower energy costs. Nevertheless, some interviewees consider that they are not able to use the service' full potential mainly due to their lack of knowledge regarding Re:dy functionalities.

How do they evaluate re:dy service

- These interviewees perceive that re:dy globally meets their expectations, because it contributes for them to lower energy costs, as it :
 - Allows interviewees to identify appliances with excessive consumption;
 - Provides information (mainly on re:dy service monthly report) that interviewees can use to analyze and understand how they can reduce energy expenses, so some of them are actually managing to reduce costs/save money with the re:dy service
- Nevertheless, some of these interviewees consider they aren't able to use the service' total potential due to:
 - **Lack of knowledge regarding the service' functionalities** (don't know the functionalities or don't know how to set them up/use them) and perceive that they don't have access to information or help tools that help them to surpass this easily ;
 - Perceived Plugs limitations (ex. excessive size and low signal capability);
 - Inability to use some of the service functionalities due to not having plugs or having a reduced number of plugs (doesn't allow to control the main household appliances).
- And therefore the involvement and interest in this service tends to decrease.

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Producers Basic Users typology tends to have some similarities to the Basic Users typology however they are more focused on controlling energy production as well as energy consumption.

Who are they?

- **Interviewees aged between 52- 63 years old** that tend to **have a low or medium knowledge of the re:dy service.**
 - They are aware of some functionalities however they tend not to know how to use them and don't seem to have really explored this service.

For what purpose do they use Re:dy Service?

- **The main focus is to control their production level as well as their energy consumption** (i.e. detect production deviations, absence of production, check if consumption is according with the forecast, ...).
 - In this context, they can use the information provided by the re:dy service to detect variances in energy consumption or in production and proactively adopt measures to correct it.
 - This tends to be specially important to detect absence of production as this might mean a problem in the production system.
 - In some cases they also use the information provided to manually implement energy efficiency measures like using Plug-In Timers to use equipment in off peak hours.

Producers Basic Users tend to access to Re:dy Service weekly or biweekly from home or work mainly through their computer. Since they tend to have low knowledge about Re:dy functionalities, they tend to not value the plugs owning only one or even none.

How do they use Re:dy Service?

Frequency of access to re:dy service:

- **Weekly or biweekly** from home or work mainly through their computer but also tablet and smartphone.
 - The access through computer perceptively allows them to have access to a wider range of information, and also it is perceived as being a faster than the access through Smartphones/Tablets.
 - A interviewee also values the access through Smartphones or Tablets as it allows him to access the portal anywhere.

Devices:

- These interviewees tend to own one plug, or none at all and don't have a re:dy meter.
 - These interviewees tend not to know the functionalities and therefore don't value the plugs and/or consider the plugs to expensive to justify the investment.
 - Some interviewees aren't aware of the existence of the a re:dy meter.

Producers Basic Users tend to use frequently the Control household energy consumption and energy production as well as the consumption and production forecasts functionalities; and are globally satisfied with Re:dy Service since allows them control energy production and consumption.

What functionalities do they tend to use?

- Globally, these interviewees tend to value functionalities that helps them monitor their production levels as well their consumption (such as compare production and consumption in different months, forecasts...).
- In this sense, they tend to use a smaller number of functionalities, about 1 to 3.
- **More frequently used:**
 - Control household energy consumption and energy production;
 - To check/validate the EDP invoice.
 - Consumption and production forecasts (in € and Kw)
- **Less frequently used:**
 - Set up notices (Power cut off, absence of solar production).

How do they evaluate re:dy service

- Globally, these users are satisfied because the service tends to meets their expectations allowing them to control energy production and consumption .

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Producers Heavy Users typology tends to have some similarities to the Heavy Users typology however these interviewees are also focused on controlling energy production as well as optimize energy consumption

Who are they?

- Interviewees aged between 35 and 42 years old that tend to have a medium or high knowledge of the re:dy service.

For what purpose do they use Re:dy Service?

- Clients that use the service to monitor both their production and consumption, as well as actively manage their energy consumption.
 - Globally these clients tend to explore the service not only to control and analyze their energy production and consumption but to use the service functionalities to maximize their energy efficiency and to reduce the costs with energy.

Producers Heavy Users tend to access to Re:dy Service several times a day through Laptop but also Smartphone to keep up to date on their energy production levels but also to gather detailed information about their energy consumption so that they can manage it more efficiently

How do they use Re:dy Service?

Frequency of access to re:dy service:

- **Several times a day or weekly** from home or work mainly through their computer but also smartphone.
 - The access through the computer is perceived as faster.
 - Globally, they use the service not only to keep up to date on their energy production levels, but also, they feel the need to know and interact actively according to their detailed consumption expenses, and they rely on the service to gather detailed information about their consumption so that they can manage it more efficiently.

Devices:

- These clients tend to own 1 to 4 plugs and don't have a re:dy meter. However one of the interviewees shown interest to acquire a re:dy meter to be able to use more functionalities.

Producers Heavy Users tend to value functionalities that helps them to manage their energy consumption such as control household energy consumption and energy production and consumption and production forecasts.

What functionalities do they tend to use?

These interviewees tend to value functionalities that helps them to manage their energy consumption, such as:

- **More frequently used:**
 - Control household energy consumption and energy production;
 - To check/validate the EDP invoice.
 - Consumption and production forecasts (in € and Kw)
- **Less frequently used:**
 - Set up notices (Power cut off, absence of solar production).
 - Control a household appliance's energy consumption
 - Remotely turn on/off a household appliance /electric equipment
 - Simulate best tariff and most suitable electric power;
 - Set up Operating Profiles (ex. out of home, in Holidays)

Producers Heavy Users are globally satisfied with Re:dy Service, however their expectation is to receive more information about the energy consumption per household division/ room.

How do they evaluate re:dy service

- Globally satisfied and somewhat involved: service meets their expectations allowing them to control energy production and consumption and to optimize household energy consumption.
- The greater the number of functionalities interviewees use the more involved and satisfied they tend to be with this service.
- However these interviewees also identify some service' limitation/areas for improvement:
 - Lack of information regarding energy consumption per household division/room;
 - Service with low awareness.

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Observers Users tend to have a low knowledge about the Re:dy Service and tend to use the service only to monitor energy consumption. The interaction with the service is almost limited to the monthly analysis of the re:dy report .

Who are they?

- An interviewee with 46 years old that as very low knowledge of the re:dy service.

For what purpose do they use Re:dy Service?

- The re:dy service is used exclusively to monitor energy consumption.
- This user access the re:dy portal rarely and the interaction with this service is very punctual almost completely limited to the analysis of the re:dy monthly report.

How do they evaluate re:dy service

- The main strength identified in the service is the **access to real time information/consumptions** and the constant data update.
- However the **service is perceived as expensive** and in this context this user is somewhat unsatisfied with this .
- This interaction of this interviewee with the service is perceptively limited by not having plugs or a re:dy meter and by his lack of knowledge of the functionalities (ex. isn't aware of the notice of power went off).

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Re:dy plugs tend to be highly valued and desired as perceptively only with this equipment interviewees can benefit of the service full potential

In terms of re:dy meter equipment/ accessories to access and interact with re:dy service :

- These equipment/accessories tend to be highly valued and desired by the great majority of interviewees as perceptively only with these devices they have access to all the re:dy service functionalities .
- Furthermore, the greater the number of plugs that the interviewees have, the more electric devices they can control and the more benefits they can obtain from the re:dy service.
- However some limitations were identified:
 - **Price per plug is perceived as too high** to allow interviewees to purchase extra re:dy plugs;
 - **Size** – re:dy plugs have an excessive size for some locations of the house (ex. home appliances close to the wall);
 - This tends to be emphasized by interviewees that don't know the re:dy meter so aren't aware of this option for controlling a electric circuit.
 - **Limited signal** – re:dy plugs lose signal if in a larger distance from the modem.
- And some interviewees also have experienced some problems:
 - Difficulty in pairing the plugs (the manual/info that comes with the plugs is perceived by some interviewees as unclear and too technical) ,
 - Reading failure – Sometimes the system is unable to read a plug (mainly Heavy Users) ;
 - Malfunction of the scheduling of plugs (don't turn on/off) generates excessive energy consumption.

The Meter is perceived as having the same function that a Plug since unable to control an electric equipment. For some interviewees an essential tool to have total control over the household energy consumption.

In terms re:dy meter equipment/ accessories to access and interact with re:dy service :

- This equipment/ accessory tends to be only known by Heavy Users (even one interviewee with this equipment does not know it's name or it's function).
- Globally perceived as having the same function that a plug - to control an electric equipment, but in this case to control built in electric equipment (ac).
- And, in this sense for some interviewees it isn't really necessary in their home, for others it's an essential tool to have total control over the household energy consumption.
- However this device is perceived as very expensive and, in this sense, interviewees hesitate or even reject to purchase it.

The perceptively high cost of these devices leads some interviewees (mainly Basic Users and Producers Basic Users) to search for more affordable alternatives with perceived as similar results such as acquiring Plug-In Timers.

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Smartphones tend to be the main device that Heavy Users and Producers Heavy Users typologies use to access and to interact with Re:dy service.

In terms of devices to access and interact with re:dy service :

- Mainly used by Heavy Users and Producers Heavy Users.

Main advantages:

- Allows them to access re:dy service all most relevant information (ex. consumption and forecast)and functionalities (turn on/off an electric equipment/profile) at anytime from anywhere (they always have their smartphone with tem)

Usage barriers /limitations:

- Not all service functionalities are available on the APP.
 - However as smartphone tends to be the main device that some interviewees use to access the re:dy service they consider that all information and functionalities off the service should be available on the APP.
- Notices aren't available on the APP.
- APP loses login when the internet connection/signal is weaker
- (Producers Heavy Users) Iphone App – doesn't show real time energy production

The computer is mainly used by Basic Users and Producers Basic Users typologies mainly because all re:dy Service functionalities and information are accessible in this device. The Tablet is mainly used by Heavy Users and Producers Heavy Users typologies as an alternative to Smartphone.

In terms of devices to access and interact with re:dy service :

- Mainly used by Basic Users and Producers Basic Users.

Main advantages:

- All service functionalities and information are accessible in this device (some information and functionalities are only available in this device specially in terms of energy production)
 - Thus, Heavy Users only tend to access re:dy service through this device when they need to configure or change some service functionalities settings – (e.g. program plugs, create a profile, etc...).
 - (For some interviewees) a quicker access and way to interact with re:dy service (vs smartphone and tablet)

- Mainly used by Heavy Users and Producers Heavy Users as an alternative to smartphone.
- Perceived as very accessible (vs. PC) and easy to use.

The majority of interviewees consider that the current ways they have to access Re:dy service cover all their needs. In this context, having access to Re:dy Service through TV tends to be perceived as useless.

Regarding the possibility of accessing re:dy service in their television:

(Majority)
Tend to not value the access to Re:dy service on TV

- This option as perceptively low relevance for the majority of interviewees as:
 - ... the existing ways to interact with re:dy service are considered sufficient and this alternative does not seem to bring added value;
 - ...they tend to have less positive experiences with other functionalities available at the TV as the APP tends to be slower and the interaction tends to be limited (arrows and number).

(Minority)
Value the access to Re:dy service on TV

- One more option to interact with the re:dy service that might be interesting and relevant as it allows:
 - Viewing the re:dy service portal comfortably seated in their sofa;
 - To present/show the re:dy service to all family and make them aware of the important of saving energy.

However when programing this access it's important to have in mind that the number of steps to reach an information or to program a functionality have to be reduced as entering menus/different pages tends to be time consuming in this access.

Additional ways to access re:dy service information

A phone contact with a IVR response that allows them to know the daily consumption but also turn on/off re:dy plugs and turn on/off usage profiles.

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The Re:dy service portal is perceived as a user friendly and intuitive portal with well structured and detailed information

- Globally, the re:dy service portal tends to be very well evaluated by the great majority of interviewees as:
 - **Browsing through the portal tends to be perceived as intuitive**
 - Presents **detailed, well-structured** and **easy-to-interpret information**,
 - Has a **layout perceived as user-friendly**.
 - Easily allows interviewees to:
 - **Monitor and control energy consumptions and production**,
 - **Monitor and control plugs/household appliances** (mainly Heavy Users and Producers Heavy Users)
- Additionally, some of the current **analysis tools available on the portal tend to surprise /exceed the expectations of some interviewees**.

“The Portal seems easy to me, although nowadays I’m really used to this system. The learning curve is fast. In the beginning I’ve had some doubts on searching for the functionalities (if they were on the tab ‘My House’ or ‘Power Efficiency’), but I got used to that over time, and now it seems simple and obvious to me. The service is according to my expectations, my goal was to monitor and control Plugs and that is easy with our current interface.” (Heavy Users typology, Male, 35 years old)

The home screen is well evaluated since it allows to have immediate access to the information perceived as more relevant.

Home Screen:

- Mainly perceived as a **very good starting point**, as it displays the most relevant information in a **direct and easy to interpret** way, as it includes:

Consumptions current situation

Consumptions forecasts/previews

Active Profiles
(Heavy Users)

and it also shows their energy production (Producers Profile only).

- Also, the animated counter graphics are perceived as appealing.

Nevertheless, there are also some aspects that can be improved in this page namely:

- Include the forecast for the current month in euros (not just in kWh);
- Include a line with average energy consumption so it can be easier to detect deviations;
- Include the on time consumption for each re:dy meter plug (Heavy Users);
- Include a meter with the total value of the energy consumption and production so it can be easier for interviewees to check the EDP invoice.
- Create the possibility for users to customize the Home screen.

The Active Management menu is important for interviewees of the Heavy Users typology since it includes functionalities that helps them to manage their energy consumption.

On “Energy Efficiency” tab:

Active Management menu:

- This menu was referred and is valued mainly by interviewees Heavy Users.
- Perceptively it includes **tools that allow interviewees not only to monitor but to control energy consumption** which is valued as it perceptively **helps them to better manage energy consumption and to reduce costs.**

“My Notifications” tab:

- A menu valued by the amount of notices available.
- This was surprising for some interviewees that tend to only access the service through the app where perceptively this menu hasn't got the same options thus they tend not to be aware of these functionalities.

“My Consumption – Energy” is a menu mostly used and valued by interviewees Heavy Users since they are the one’s who have more re:dy plugs thus use this menu to analyze and compare the energy consumption of specific household appliances.

“My Consumption – Energy” menu:

- A easy-to-read chart,
- With **useful information** as it allows interviewees to know the energy consumption of specific household appliances where they have re:dy plugs.
- Most interviewees, consider that **including temperature on the graphic is useful**, as it perceptively helps to **optimize heating solutions** by having into account temperature (to program thermostats in order to optimize energy consumption).

Interviewees would value to have “Help” section with information that would help them not only to overcome some difficulties easier but to fully seize the service potential.

Interviewees identified some areas of improvement for the re:dy portal namely:

- **Include a Help section**, with additional information, such as:
 - **Tutorials** – with a step by step description, “how to” information (example: how physically to change their plugs and then how to program/schedule it on the Portal, specify what is maximum distance to place the plugs in order to get a good communication with the Re:dy modem)
 - Troubleshooting, how to solve the most frequent problems/issues
- **Include in the section ‘My Documents’ Section the monthly reports and consumption and production invoices as:**
 - The access of this information in the portal is perceived as complementary to the information presented by the service;
 - This portal is perceived as more accessible and easier to consult than the EDP website as interviewees tend to access this portal more frequently (are more accustomed to it).
- Create a historic with **system modifications history** and **Portal user activity**.
- Include the possibility of not only **compare a consecutive time period but also the same time period in the previous years** as perceptively as the weather conditions tend to be the same this is also a useful comparison.
- **Include the possibility of exporting data in PDF.**
- **Regarding Production Information, interviewees consider that it would be useful if:**
 - **The information of the weather conditions should be available not only when the option week is selected but also when the option yesterday and month is selected.**
 - In the graphics “Total Production” and “Average Production” the value in kWh and euros should be displayed at the same time (without having to choose one option or the other).

*“Regarding the re:dy devices, the Plugs should always inform the users of the maximum distances they can communicate with the gateway. As a priority I consider there should be some information on how to change physically the Plugs from a place to another and then how to configure on the Portal, on a Step-by-Step process.”
(Heavy Users typology Male, 40 years old)*

“I’d value to have a inbox with my invoices, both energy consumption and production. And also to see the numeric values, both production and consumption. The EDP invoice comes with numeric values, that would be good to be able to compare them with the service.” Producers Basic Users - Male, 62

*“The evaluation can increase substantially if there was a new section with customer service where there are troubleshoot videos and explain how to use the Website considering Profiles and Settings.”
(Heavy Users typology Male, 43 years old)*

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The Forecast functionality is valued due to the possibility of detecting deviations to the normal energy consumption and adopting corrective measures. Profiles are perceived as relevant for the majority of interviewees but only used by a minority of Heavy Users.

Regarding re:dy service functionalities interviewees highlighted the following:

- A valued functionality as it **allows interviewees to:**
 - Know how much they will have to pay at the end of the month
 - To identify energy consumption above average and adopt corrective measures.
- Aspects to improve:
 - The dates should be flexible, as the billing period may not coincide with the end of the month
- Include all the associated costs (final value of the invoice).

- This functionality is used only by a minority of Heavy Users for instance when on holidays or adjusted to different seasons (ex. Winter, Summer).
- The majority of interviewees aren't aware of how this functionality works or even what does it allow to achieve (some of them seem to have inaccurate information) and/or perceive that don't have enough re:dy plugs to take advantage of it.
- However, after knowing what this functionality is about, interviewees seem interested in taking advantage of the benefits of this functionality (ex. holiday profile).
- Aspects to improve:
 - Suggest profiles according to pattern of usage (week/week-end/holidays) and then allow users to customize them according to their specific needs and schedules.
 - Create the possibility of having specific schedule for each profile to activate and allow to schedule plugs within each profile.
 - Profiles have to overlap the scheduling of re:dy meter plugs operating hours (perceptively at the moment this isn't happening).

The presence simulator although useful is somewhat difficult to program. The functionality comparison of families/households tends to be perceived as a less useful functionality at the moment as it does not seem to be fully operational.

Presence simulator

- A useful functionality however difficult to program/configure.
- Also, some interviewees consider that for it to be really credible they have to have/use more than one plug.

Comparison of families/households

- This functionality is widely unknown but when exploring the portal was well received as consider interesting.
- However, based on different trials they perceive that it can't be fully operational as it provided inconsistent results probably due to a small customer base.

- Aspects to improve:

- Include the possibility to chose a period to stablish a comparison as, for instance, in the winter the energy consumption is higher.

Energy efficiency functionalities tend to be used mainly by Heavy Users and Producers Heavy Users. Basic Users generally aren't aware of these functionalities or know them but don't know how to use them.

"Energy Efficiency" Functionalities

Power and Tariff Simulator

- This functionality tends to be used mainly by Heavy Users as a **way to reduce costs by adjusting power and tariff to users specific energy consumption namely to the differences on energy consumption throughout the year.**
- Some users of the typology Producers and Basic Users aren't aware of it.
- Aspects to improve:
 - The parameters for comparison shouldn't only be the last 30 days but the same period in the last year as the weather conditions tend to be more similar.

Schedule ready meter plugs operating hours

- The possibility of programming equipment's to operate during the more economic time (off peak hours), according to the biphasic tariff tends to be very valued by interviewees as a way to reduce costs while for instance maintaining the comfort in the household in terms of temperature.
- Nevertheless, some interviewees consider that is not easy to define the schedule of the plugs and in other hand the turn on/off isn't reliable.
- Aspects to improve:
 - The icon to add or remove a line should be on the end of the list (not near the first row).
 - For this functionality to be more automatized perceptively it would be necessary to ask more information regarding the equipment where the plug is connected and also how is this equipment used/for what purpose and to include a calendar to register diary routines (peaks of usage, rhythms, absences, etc.).

Take control on the limit of contracted power is perceived as a useful functionality to reduce costs as it perceptively allows users to have a lower contracted power.

“Energy Efficiency” Functionalities

**Take control on the limit
of contracted power**

- This functionality is used only by some Heavy Users that value it as they perceive that it not only avoids a cut of power but also allows them to have a lower contracted power and pay less.

Alerts/notices are perceived as useful functionalities to draw user' attention to a potential problem and in this sense tend to be valued.

“My Notices/Alerts” Functionalities

- Some interviewees, mainly Heavy Users, are aware that the re:dy service has some pre-programmed notices/alerts that they can activate and that it also allows the user to program his own customized alerts/notices. And they tend to use and value these notices/alerts as they perceive that it will help them to be aware of any problems or issues that need to be solved or adjusted.
- On the other hand, some interviewees aren't aware of the existence of these notices/alerts.

- In this context, interviewees suggested the introduction of the following improvements in these functionalities.
 - Include a “Help” icon in this section that describes the propose of the alert/notice and explained step by step how to program it;
 - The frequency in which the alerts should be sent should be defined by the user and all alerts should be displayed in the APP.
 - Include additional ways for the user to receive the alert/notice namely a notice in the App and an SMS when the Alert/notice is set as very important/urgent so they can immediately see it and react accordingly.
 - Absence of Production alert: perceptively this notice/alert is only received after 48 hours without production, however the interviewees producers would like to receive a notice/alert when there's no production in hours that generally there should be production (sunny hours);
 - Energy cut off alert: if the it's a general cut off, the notice/alert should include the estimated time for power to be restored.
- Other notices/alerts suggested as it might indicate a problem were:
 - Peak consumption;
 - Energy consumption above average
 - Change in energy consumption pattern in the lasts 6 months;
 - Electric equipment/home appliance malfunction.
 - Turn on/off a specific equipment/home appliance.
- And also a information when the reading was register to be billed.

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Heavy Users tend to suggest new functionalities that increase comfort in the household and control over the household electric equipment.

Besides suggesting improvements on the existing functionalities, interviewees (mainly Heavy Users) also recommended new potential useful functionalities for the re:dy service:

- Household temperature control by measuring the temperature inside the home using sensors and manage the heating and air conditioning equipment's so the temperature will remain at a pre-defined temperature or having in consideration pre-defined parameters (ex. Turn on the heating if the temperature is bellow 15° or turn on the heating if the temperature between 22pm and 07h59 am is bellow 20°).
- Household alarm based on the re:dy service with sensors and cameras and with a competitive price;
- Simulate infrared signals in order to manage equipment's that only work through a remote control;
- Automatic opening/ closing shutters;
- Proactively provide suggestions to save energy;
- Provide information of energy consumption by room;
- Provide emergency battery to avoid energy damages on important equipment's in power cuts;
- Present comparative of energy consumption between different electric equipment/home appliances.

The possibility of re:dy service to learn with users operations (an be more proactive) is welcomed by the majority of interviewees.

Interviewees consider that this idea is consistent with functionality's already present in the re:dy, it conveys the idea that the service continues to evolve which can generate more interest and involvement with the re:dy service and help justify the service monthly fee.

Also, for them it and can be a good way for them to better manage their energy consumption and take advantage of the full potential of the re:dy service with less effort, to save money and energy.

However, for the majority of interviewees it's important that the service provides suggestions that are depending on users approval (can't be intrusive).

- In this context, interviewees expect that:
 - The suggestions provided by the re:dy service will be adjusted not only to their energy consumption patterns but also for the type and number of equipment they own (ex. 2 plugs and 1 re:dy meter).
- Thus, this idea is value by different typologies of interviewees since:
 - In Basic Users opinion, this functionality would help to overcome the difficulties related to the lack of knowledge to manage the service;
 - In other hand, for Heavy Users this automation of the process would optimized the service and reduce the time needed to manage it;

However

- The participants advise that suggestions should be firstly accepted and validated by the user, it means, the system shouldn't be intrusive;
- This kind of initiatives should be considered carefully to avoid the risk of redundancies;
- The mains advantages have to be firstly explained to users.

Proactive suggestions to improve the management of energy consumption and reduce or avoid unnecessary costs.

In this context, interviewees have suggested the following examples of proactive recommendations for the service to provide:

- Suggest energy efficiency measures and present its benefits;
- Identify plugs with excessive energy consumption;
- Detect energy consumption above average and suggest corrective measures to adjust consumption;
- Suggest profiles based on the user's specific consumption.
- Suggest the best schedule to program the functioning of a electric equipment/household appliance (more economic);
- Recommend the best tariff and power contracted according with users energy consumption;
- Automatically adjust the consumption to the biphasic schedule;
- Indicate when to turn on/off equipment's to avoid unnecessary costs;
- Program plugs according to the user' profile.

An Online Forum to share experiences and information with others re:dy service users is a well evaluated idea by the majority of the interviewees mainly Basic Users and highly evolved Heavy Users.

The interviewees welcomed the possibility of sharing experiences with other users and, in this context, suggested the idea of having an Online Forum.

- For Heavy Users this is valued as a way to share their knowledge and experience but also to clarify doubts and to learn new ways to take advantage of the re:dy service.
- On the other hand for Basic Users it's a way for them to learn with other users with more experience, to clarify doubts to be able to take advantage of re:dy service full potential.
- In this sense the Online Forum is understood as a community of users, to share experiences related to the service, and it should:
 - ...allow user to share ideas and read suggestions posted by others users. Nevertheless the community and its content should be manage and controlled by EDP
 - ... be only for re:dy service users with a restrict access (by e-mail, password)
 - ...include an with a ethic code regarding participation.
 - ... be organized by topics and users issues, such as instructions, energy saving and efficiency (measures/examples), suggestions and solutions to solve installation and configuration issues, etc.
- To communicate the Online Forum the service should send an invitation by e-mail to users or include the invitation in the monthly report with a the link to the forum.
- In this context, Basic Users and some Producers would regularly access the online forum to clarify doubts and learn about the service.
- On the other hand, some Heavy Users that are highly evolved with the service will access the Online forum to share ideas but other don't feel they would access the forum since they prefer other (more institutional) ways to clarify doubts.

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Overall, interviewees project the future of re:dy service as...

For Heavy Users the need to acquire more plugs tends to be the main challenge to increase involvement with this service. To overcome this challenge a re:dy service campaign “Bring a friend to join re:dy service and win a plug...” and the possibility of acquiring plugs and re:dy meter with the cost divided in monthly payments could also be good ideas to increase re:dy service involvement.

Heavy Users & Producers Heavy Users

Challenges

- **Lack of a sufficient number of plugs that allows interviewees to manage all the main electric equipment**
- **Lack of knowledge/usage of functionalities that aren't available in the APP**
- **Lack of knowledge information regarding some functionalities** (interviewees that aren't sure if they are using the functionalities correctly)
- **Interviewees that perceive that they already use the re:dy service to its fullest** (all the relevant functionalities)

How to increase involvement and interaction with Re:dy Service

- Re:dy service campaign “Bring a friend to join re:dy service and win a plug,... bring two friends and win a re:dy meter”
 - Some Heavy Users perceive that, at the moment, they already use all re:dy service functionalities that they can have taking into account the number of plugs they own.
 - However, heavy users tend to desire to have total control of the main electric equipment's but tend to refuse to spend more in equipment.
 - They tend to be tech savvy and have an extended knowledge of the service.
 - In this context, heavy users can be re:dy service advocates, promoting this service among potential clients while winning more equipment that allows to continue to further interact with the re:dy service: a win-win partnership
- Possibility of acquiring plugs and re:dy meter with the cost divided in monthly payments.
- All re:dy service functionalities should be available through the APP or should be communicated in the re:dy monthly report with a link or a description where these functionalities are available so users that only tend to access re:dy service in their smartphone also know and user these functionalities.
- Video Tutorials (You tube): for instance “How to schedule plugs?”.
- Live Chat Assistance in the re:dy service portal.
- Create and communicate new functionalities such as Household temperature control .

The lack of knowledge of the existing functionalities and/or how to use them tends to be the main challenge for Basic Users. To overcome this challenge it's important to create Video Tutorials, a Live Chat Assistance in the re:dy service portal and an Online Forum where clients can share experiences and clarify doubts.

**Basic Users
&
Producers
Basic Users**

Challenges

- **Lack of knowledge of the existing functionalities and/or how to use them**
- **Lack of knowledge of the existing equipment and/or how to use them**
- **Lack of a plugs or a sufficient number of plugs to use some functionalities**

How to increase involvement and interaction with Re:dy Service

- Presentation of the functionalities on the monthly re:dy report with main benefits and with a link or a description where these functionalities are available.
- Video Tutorials (You tube): for instance "How to activate an alert?"
- Online Forum where clients can share experiences and clarify doubts.
- Presentation of the existing equipment (mainly re:dy meter) on the monthly re:dy report with main benefits and with a link or a description how they can purchase/subscribe to these equipment.
- Video Tutorials (You tube): to for instance "How to schedule plugs?"
- Online Forum where clients can share experiences and clarify doubts.
- Plugs promotions;
- System of rewards with plugs as the prize.

To attract new costumers it's important to convey mainly in **Bellow the Line** in specialized magazines and website with a message mainly focused on re:dy service main advantages, principally related to energy saving, control and cost reduction but also focused on the technological aspects of the service

What message to convey?

- Costs reduction
- Energy saving
- Energy consumption control

• **The message should be focused on:**

- Re:dy service main advantages, principally related to energy saving, control and cost reduction but also focused on the technological aspects of the service.
- Costs and energy management
 - “Control your energy consumption, with no surprises on the end of the month”
 - “People like to control, have more for less and share their success with their friends and family”

Where communicate?

Communicate mainly *Bellow the Line*

- Magazines specialized in technology/trends;
- Weekly Magazines (ex. Visão, Sábado)
- Newspapers (ex. Expresso, Económico, Jornal de Negócios)
- Banners and Pop-ups in news, technology, games websites
- EDP website (namely Client area) and Invoice
- Museum of Electricity – to allow users or potential clients to explore different functionalities focused on the idea of saving energy and energy efficiency with interactive games for children; a contest to win the re:dy service for a year etc.

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Main Objectives and Methodology

Project Objectives:

- To understand clients experience with the re:dy service:
- Identify ways to improve re:dy service and generate more interaction with the service

Methodology:

In this context, we conducted an **Online Community** from **22nd of June until the 31st of July** with **16 re:dy service clients**.

Online Forum Re:dy Service

Qualitative Study

September, 2015

DCMK

TNS